

THE MASTITIS REVOLUTION NEW APPROCHES TO AN OLD PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

Mastitis, an inflammatory reaction of the mammary gland that is usually caused by a microbial infection, is recognized as the most costly disease in dairy cattle. Decreased milk production accounts for approximately 70% of the total cost of mastitis. Mammary tissue damage reduces the number and activity of epithelial cells and consequently contributes to decreased milk production. Mammary tissue damage has been shown to be induced by either apoptosis or necrosis. These 2 distinct types of cell death can be distinguished by morphological, biochemical, and molecular changes in dying cells. Both bacterial factors and host immune reactions contribute to epithelial tissue damage. During infection of the mammary glands, the tissue damage can initially be caused by bacteria and their products. Certain bacteria produce toxins that destroy cell membranes and damage milk-producing tissue, whereas other bacteria are able to invade and multiply within the

bovinemammary epithelial cells before causing cell death. The current review focuses on the main pathogens that cause this inflammation and their prevalence as well as strategies to prevent their proliferation. We discuss economic loss, with the goal of demonstrating that prevention is always better than disease management.

KEYWORDS: Animal mastitis, dairy animals, mammary gland damage, NSAIDs, Herbal medicines.

I. INTRODUCTION

What is mean by mastitis

Mastitis is defined as an inflammation of the mammary gland. Mastitis usually occurs primarily in response to intramammary bacterial infection, but also to intramammary mycoplasmal, fungal, or algal infections. Mechanical trauma, thermal trauma, and chemical insult predispose the gland to intramammary infection (IMI). Occurrence of mastitis depends on the interaction of host, agent, and environmental factors.

History of mastitis and physical

Lactation Mastitis Clinical Features

Lactation mastitis is often preceded by either engorgement or a focally blocked duct. Patients may give a history of these associated symptoms before developing the classic features of mastitis. Lactation mastitis is characterized by a focal, firm, erythematous, swollen, and painful area of 1 breast and systemic symptoms, including fever with a temperature ≥ 100.4 °F (38 °C), tachycardia, chills, myalgias, and malaise.^[1]

Nonlactational Mastitis Clinical Features

Features of PDM include a periareolar or subareolar mass, which may be associated with pain and erythema. Patients may present with nipple inversion, a thick nipple discharge, a breast abscess, or draining fistulas. The clinical features of PDM vary based on the duration of the condition. Acute PDM resembles acute suppurative mastitis as the affected breast is erythematous, swollen, warm, and painful, with abscesses often forming. Systemic symptoms, including fever and malaise, may be pronounced, reflecting a more severe inflammatory response. Subacute PDM typically has systemic symptoms which have subsided, but localized signs persist. A palpable lump may remain, and the overlying skin may appear dark red. Long-standing PDM cases are characterized by deep-seated masses, frequently located in the areolar region, with cycles of flare-ups and remission; in severe cases, chronic sinus tracts and persistent draining wounds may develop.^[2]

IGM typically presents as a tender, erythematous, and unilateral soft breast mass that can occur in any breast quadrant except for the region beneath the areola. Common symptoms include nipple discharge, skin changes such as ulcers or sinus formation, and enlargement of the axillary lymph nodes, particularly in chronic cases. Approximately 34% of individuals with IGM experience systemic symptoms beyond the breast, including joint swelling, joint pain, and nodular erythema, often affecting the lower extremities.^[2]

A grading system was developed that correlated the severity of IGM with clinical features and breast mass size. Mild IGM is characterized by a breast mass <2 cm with no associated ulcers or fistulas and minimal pain. Moderate IGM involves a breast mass measuring between 2 and 5 cm, with fluid collections that may require aspiration drainage, 1 fistula, and a small amount of discharge. Severe IGM is identified by a breast mass >5 cm, severe pain, the presence of multiple fistulas, and ulcers that discharge >20 mL daily. This system is instrumental in evaluating the extent of the disease and determining appropriate treatment strategies.^[2]

Mastitis is a disease characterized by swelling, heat, redness, hardness, pain, and aberrant milk due to physiological, chemical, and cellular changes in milk and pathological changes in udder tissue.^[3,4] The most common dairy production disease is mastitis. According to the livestock economy assessment of 2023-2024, livestock can provide 1.82% of our gross domestic product (GDP) and mastitis causes losing millions of liters of milk. It estimated that each individual must drink 250 ml/day of milk, but the supply is reduced to 193.38 ml/day if the mastitis uncontrolled.^[5] Untreated mastitis in dairy herds has substantial economic effects due to decreased milk quantity and quality, and hygiene. Mastitis also negatively impacts the days of first heat after parturition and calving interval.^[6,7] Clinically, there were clinical and subclinical mastitis. Clinical mastitis characterizes by clinical signs, while subclinical is not, making it more economically important. Milk pockets like Sirajganj (42.7%) have a higher mastitis rate than non-milk pockets.^[8,9] Mastitis affects the economy greatly. Epidemiological studies suggested that mastitis costs INR1390 per lactation, with 49% related to milk supply reduction and 37% to veterinary expenses in India. Crossbred cows and buffaloes lost INR 700 and INR 364 due to milk output reduction.^[10,11] Livestock GDP is 82,014 Crore Taka, and 20% and 50% of people depend on it directly and partly, respectively.^[5] We will not meet our milk and nutrition needs if we cannot control economic diseases like mastitis. This review underlines the essential need for an organised strategy in mastitis control, integrating scientific advancements with efficient on-farm approaches in order to protect Bangladesh's dairy industry from this persistent issue.

TYPES OF MASTITIS

Depending on the infection pattern, mastitis is of different types; contagious and environmental with a broad spectrum of microbes. Besides the above types, it can be subclinical or clinical.^[12,13] Contagious mastitis is generated from inflected ones and

contaminated to healthy cows by the time of milking through hands. It can also spread through improper sanitization of milking machines or by cloths used during milking but in environmental mastitis, the causal pathogens originate from cowsheds, unhealthy filthy water for preparation of udder prior to milking, flies, mud holes.^[13] Intramammary infections (IMIS) were diagnosed as SCM. However, it is difficult to identify SCM as initially it appears inside without any visible inflammation or redness in the udder or teat but an increase of somatic cells in the milk act as an indicator.^[14] The occurrence of SCM was ~32.48% and considerably lowers in clinical mastitis 9.4%.^[15] SCM could not be noticed so easily but is always associated with loss of milk in the dairy herd.^[16] Traditional and advanced therapies are applicable for the control of mastitis. The treatments were through bacteriocins, nanoparticle based, vaccination, antibiotics, and phytotherapy. These therapies are not effective because multiple factors (host, pathogen, and environment) are responsible for the disease.^[17] To date for curing mastitis, the broad-spectrum antibiotics were used as the common therapy. However, the consequence of this antibiotic therapy is the drug resistance microbes. Substitutes for this type of therapy were explored by many researchers.^[18,19] Thus, herbal therapy for mastitis treatment is an accurate alternative to be replaced for synthetic drug.^[20]

CAUSES OF MASTITIS

Fig. 1: Basic Causes of Mastitis.

Microbial pathogens of mastitis Many mastitis pathogens are identified to dates, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus agalactiae* and other *Streptococcus spp*^[22,23] *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* is a major causal microbe reported in the case of SCM in bovine herds followed by *Clostridium perfringens*, *Mycobacterium*, *Mycoplasma*, *Prototheca*,

Pasturella, Nocardia asteroides, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Staphylococcus aureus and yeasts.^[24] Actinomyces spp., Staphylococcus spp. and Streptococcus spp. are some pathogenic bacteria isolated from bovine mastitis.^[25] Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus agalactiae and Mycoplasma spp. are contagious bacteria causing contagious mastitis.^[21] Microorganisms that cause mastitis are categorised into three categories; 1. Contagious (Corynebacterium bovis, Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus agalactiae, Mycoplasma sp.) 2. Environmental (Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Klebsiella oxytoca, Streptococcus uberis, Streptococcus bovis, Streptococcus dysgalactiae, Citrobacter sp. and Serratia sp.) and 3. Other (Coagulase-negative Staphylococci sp., Arcanobacterium pyogenes, Candida sp., Nocardia asteroides, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Prototheca sp. and Serratia sp.)^[26] Staphylococcus aureus is predominant in mastitis samples as reported by many workers.^[27,28] Escherichia spp. (22.16%), Klebsiella spp. (1.47%), Pasteurella spp. (2.45%), Pseudomonas spp. (0.45%) Staphylococcus aureus (20.19%), Streptococcus spp. (13.3%), Streptococcus agalactiae (12.8%) and Streptococcus dysgalactiae (0.5%) are the most common pathogens isolated from mastitis milk sample.^[29] Staphylococcus, Aerococcus, Streptococcus, Enterobacter, Micrococcus, Corynebacterium, Acinetobacter, Psychrobacter, Ignavigranum, and Atopostipes are the bacteria species which are found to be causative pathogen for bovine mastitis. Staphylococcus spp. and Streptococcus spp. are maximum contaminants amongst all these.^[30] Escherichia coli, Klebsiella spp. and Staphylococcus aureus are isolated from the mastitis milk sample.^[31] Escherichia coli, Klebsiella oxytoca, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus uberis, Streptococcus dysgalactiae, and Staphylococcus aureus are isolated and identified from samples collected from mastitis cow.^[33] The most predominant bacterial pathogen responsible for the high prevalence in both subclinical and clinical mastitis was S. aureus followed by E. coli and S. agalactiae. The frequency of mastitis due to fungi and yeast was found to be very less as compared to the bacterial pathogens.^[32] Overuse of antibiotics and poor sanitation contributes to yeast mastitis.^[29]

The following points are some causes that might lead to mastitis in animals^[48]

- Age: Infection rates rise with age, reaching a peak at 7 years old.
- Herd size: larger herds have a higher incidence.
- Breed: Crossbred and exotic cows are more likely to be affected than zebu cows.

The incidence has been observed to be higher in Holstein Friesian cows than in Jersey cows.

- Stage of breastfeeding: The first and last stages of lactation have higher infection rates.

- High-yielders of milk are more frequently impacted than low-yielders.
- Nutrition: A high-protein diet may operate as a risk factor. Selenium, vitamin A, and vitamin E could all play a role in mastitis resistance.
- Milking frequency and udder structure: An increased risk of intramammary infection has been linked to a high milking frequency and a large teat canal diameter. Differences in mastitis are also assumed to be related to variations in udder depth, teat length, shape, and orifice morphology.
- Hygiene: Poor sanitation and hygiene contribute to the growth of microorganisms.

PATHOGENESIS

Mastitis in dairy animals occurs when the udder becomes inflamed and bacteria invade the teat canal and mammary glands. These bacteria multiply and produce toxins that cause injury to the milk secreting tissue, besides, physical trauma and chemical irritants. These cause increase in the number of leukocytes, or somatic cells in the milk, reducing its quantity and adversely affecting the quality of milk and milk by-products. The teat end serves as the first line of defense against infection. From outside, a sphincter of smooth muscles surrounds the teat canal which functions to keep the teat canal closed.^[34] It also prevents milk from escaping, and bacteria from entering into the teat. From inside, the teat canal is lined with keratin derived from stratified squamous epithelium. Damage to keratin has been reported to cause increased susceptibility of teat canal to bacterial invasion and colonization.^[35] The keratin is a waxy material composed of fatty acids and fibrous proteins in the teat. The fatty acids are both esterified and non-esterified, representing myristic acid, palmitoleic acid and linolenic acid which are bacteriostatic.^[36]

The fibrous proteins of keratin in the teat canal bind electrostatically to mastitis pathogens, which alter the bacterial cell wall, rendering it more susceptible to osmotic pressure. Inability to maintain osmotic pressure causes lysis and death of invading pathogens.^[34,36] The keratin structure thus enables trapping of invading bacteria and prevents their migration into the gland cistern.^[37] During milking, bacteria present near the opening of the teat find opportunity to enter the teat canal, causing trauma and damage to the keratin or mucous membranes lining the teat sinus.^[38] The canal of a teat may remain partially open for 1-2 hour after milking and during this period the pathogens may freely enter into the teat canal.^[39]

Bacterial pathogens which are able to traverse the opening of teat end by escaping antibacterial activities establish the disease process in the mammary gland which is the

second line of defense of the host. In dairy animals, the mammary gland has a simple system consisting of teats and udder, where the bacteria multiply and produce toxins, enzymes and cell-wall components which stimulate the production of inflammatory mediators attracting phagocytes. The severity of inflammatory response, however, is dependent upon both the host and pathogen factors. The pathogen factors include the species, virulence, strain and the size of inoculum of bacteria, whereas the host factors include parity, the stage of lactation, age and immune status of the animal, as well as the somatic cell count.

Neutrophils are the predominant cells found in the mammary tissue and mammary secretions during early stage of mastitis and constitute >90% of the total leukocytes.^[40] The phagocytes move from the bone marrow toward the invading bacteria in large numbers attracted by chemical messengers or chemotactic agents such as cytokines, complement and prostaglandins released by damaged tissues.^[41,42] The neutrophils exert their bactericidal effect through a respiratory burst and produce hydroxyl and oxygen radicals that kill the bacteria. During phagocytosis, bacteria are also exposed to several oxygen-independent reactants such as peroxidases, lysozymes, hydrolytic enzymes and lactoferrin. In addition to their phagocytic activities, neutrophils are a source of antibacterial peptides called defensins, killing a variety of pathogens that cause mastitis.^[43] Masses of neutrophils pass between the milk producing cells into the lumen of the alveoli, thus increasing the somatic cell counts and also damaging the secretory cells. Increased number of leukocytes in milk causes increase in the number of somatic cells. Clots are formed by aggregation of leukocytes and blood clotting factors which may block the ducts and prevent complete milk removal, resulting in scar formation with proliferation of connective tissue elements. This results in a permanent loss of function of that portion of the gland. The milk ducts remain clogged, secretory cells revert to non-producing state, alveoli begin to shrink and are replaced by scar tissue. This helps in formation of small pockets making difficult for antibiotics to reach there and also prevents complete removal of milk.^[39]

Macrophages are the predominant cells found in milk and tissue of healthy involuted and lactating mammary glands.^[44] Macrophages ingest bacteria, cellular debris and accumulated milk components. The phagocytic activity of macrophages can be increased in the presence of opsonic antibody for specific pathogens. Because of indiscriminate ingestion of fat, casein and milk components, the mammary gland macrophages are less effective at phagocytosis than are blood leukocytes.^[45,46] Macrophages also play a role in antigen processing and

presentation.^[47] Conditions which contribute to trauma of mammary gland include: incorrect use of udder washes, wet teats and failure to use teat dips, failure to prepare milking animals or pre milking stimulation for milk ejection, over milking, insertion of mastitis tubes or teat canulae, injury caused by infectious agents and their toxins and physical trauma.

Fig 2. mammary gland damage during mastitis.

➤ **Pathogenesis of mastitis**

a) Factors Associated with Clinical Mastitis

Milk output is linked to teat canal diameter and stretch. The higher teat canal of high-yielding cows stays open longer after milking, increasing the risk of mastitis caused by environmental pathogens like *E. coli*. Local-breed cows show lower mastitis affinity than higher-yielding cross-breeds in tropical regions (high temperature and humidity) and intensive farming practices.^[49] Lactating cows producing 1-5 and 6-10L milk had considerably greater milk output than those producing 16-20L or more milk. In cows with reproductive and periparturiant disorders, mastitis was more common. Mastitis prevalence is greater in rainy season than winter or summer (3.47%, 11.52%) and 5% in winter.^[50] Lactating calves with BCS scores >2.5–3 are more susceptible to SCM than weak bodies.^[52] Other farm-level variables including cow hygiene, farmer knowledge, and herd size can also cause mastitis.

b) Factors Associated with Sub-Clinical Mastitis

The most common farm-level SCM risk factors include unhygienic conditions, big udders, teat injuries, udder wounds, filthy milkers' hands, and inappropriate milking machine management. Breeding, teat shape, and body condition score (BCS) are controllable risk factors, however age, parity, lactation stage, and housing are not. Other sources say the biggest risk factors for mastitis include teat end-to-floor distance, pregnancy, milk output, milking stimulation, milk leakage, and floor type.^[51,52]

PREVENTION

1. Season

Highest incidence of mastitis is observed in the rainy season (62.24%) followed by the summer (26.53%) and the winter (4.08%).¹⁵ It seems that breakout of mastitis is more in low

temperature. This depicts that the bacterial growth is more suitable in low temperature climate.^[53,54]

2. Floor type of the shed

Cowshed matters much for the origin of mastitis. Earthen floor of shed makes the dairy animals maximum (48.98%) susceptible than brick floor (38.78%) and concrete floor (12.24%). Maximum occurrence of the disease is reported in the earthen floors might be due to improper cleaning and dampening.^[55] Poorly designed facilities increase the incidence of environmental mastitis^[56] Cowsheds are mostly in unhygienic condition due to obvious reasons, which plays a major role in harbouring environmental pathogens for mastitis. Due to the humid climate basement of cowshed mostly remains muddy or swampy favouring the growth of mastitis.^[57]

3. Udder type teat wise prevalence

Prevalence of mastitis is highest in cows with cup shaped udder (48.98%), then bowl shaped udder (30.61%) and round shaped udder (20.41%).^[55] Cup or pendulous udder (depending on the depth) is closer to filthy ground in unhygienic condition in a suitable basement for mastitis.^[58] Occurrence of mastitis is comparatively less in fore quarter 42.85% than hind (57.14%). Accordingly, the right hind teat is more prone (40%) than the left hind (17%), right fore 19% and left fore 24%^[55] Teat wise or udder wise contamination is more in hind part and the reason could be milk yield potential followed by contaminated hind legs and relaxed teat sphincters.^[59] Generally, in dairy cattle prevalence of mastitis in hind quarters were comparatively more due to the exposure of that part to dung and urine.^[60]

4 .Method of milking

Occurrence of mastitis is more frequent in hand milking process than the mechanised ones.^[15] Mechanised milking process is always advantageous to obtain safe and healthy milk.^[61]

5. Teat infection

Prime pathway for entry of mastitis is the teat canal. Hence attention should and must be focused on the maintenance of a healthy and clean teat. Most important is to avoid teat injury, which is a risk factor for contamination of the intra- mammary glands.^[62]

6. Use of teat infectants

Disinfectants are always advisable particularly for teat and udder which lowers a load of contaminants of mastitis proper sanitation is mandatory during the lactation period to control the spread of microbial infections and their colonial growth.^[63]

7. Dry period

There is an increased risk of clinical mastitis with longer dry period >40 days.^[64] The frequency of infection increases during the two weeks prior to calving and two weeks following drying.^[65] However, the intramammary infection is 2 to 12 times higher during the dry period.^[66]

OBJECTIVES

- Identify risk factors for acute mastitis.
- Differentiate the clinical features of each type of mastitis.
- Implement evidence-based treatment strategies for each type of acute mastitis.
- Collaborate with the interprofessional team to improve outcomes for patients affected by acute mastitis

DIAGNOSIS

• Lactational mastitis

- Breast engorgement
- Clogged duct
- Breast abscess
- Breast cyst
- Galactocele
- Phlegmon
- Inflammatory breast carcinoma
- Fat necrosis
- Lactating adenoma.^[67]

• Periductal mastitis

- Duct ecta
- Breast abscess
- Breast carcinoma

- **Idiopathic granulomatous mastitis**

- Breast carcinoma
- Autoimmune disease (eg, Wegener granulomatosis and Takayasu arteritis)
- Tuberculosis mastitis
- Sarcoidosis
- Breast abscess
- Fat necrosis
- Leprosy
- Cat scratch disease
- Fungal infections (eg, Histoplasmosis and Cryptococcosis).^{[68],[69]}

TREATMENT

NSAIDS TREATMENT

The specific mechanism of action of NSAIDs is inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX), reducing production of prostaglandins (an inflammatory mediator).^[70] COX has 2 isoforms, COX-1 and COX-2; the former is naturally expressed in all tissues, and has a role in maintaining normal physiological functions, whereas the latter is induced by inflammatory stimuli and cytokines.^[71] NSAIDs that are more selective inhibitors of COX-2 have greater therapeutic effects, whereas those that are highly selective inhibitors of COX-1 have more side effects, including an increased risk of retained placenta, uterine inflammation, and gastric irritation.^[72]

The NSAIDs used to treat bovine mastitis include flunixin meglumine, meloxicam, ketoprofen, and carprofen. Flunixin meglumine, the only NSAID approved by FDA in the US for dairy cows to control fever associated with mastitis and endotoxemia associated with *E. coli* mastitis, is commonly used as an analgesic in US food animals.^[73,74] It inhibits both COX-1 and COX-2, but is more selective for COX-1, thereby increasing risk of retained placenta and digestive disorders.^[71] However, using only a single dose of flunixin meglumine can reduce these side effects.^[75] In cows with lipopolysaccharide-induced mastitis, flunixin meglumine increased feeding time and rumination during the first 9 and 12 h, and improved ruminal activity.^[76,77] In addition, flunixin meglumine decreased blood nonesterified fatty acids and Isop concentrations in cows with *E. coli* mastitis, indicating a reduced inflammatory response.^[76]

Meloxicam is a more selective inhibitor of COX-2, greatly avoiding side effects associated with COX-1 inhibition.^[78] In a randomized trial on 2,653 cows from 20 herds, 1 mg/kg meloxicam orally at calving reduced the incidence of subclinical mastitis, increased feed intake and milk production, and reduced systemic inflammation.^[79] Furthermore, meloxicam alleviated the pain of LPS-induced clinical mastitis, mitigated udder edema, and reduced rectal temperature.^[80] When meloxicam was used to treat mild to moderate mastitis in the first 120 days of lactation, calving interval of infected cows were reduced, and the conception rate of infected cows was improved, which had positive benefits for pasturebased dairy production.^[81] Ketoprofen inhibits both COX-1 and COX-2^[82] and has been used for treatment of bovine mastitis due to its rapid onset of action, short plasma half-life, low toxicity, and no milk withdrawal. It has been approved for use in Canada, Brazil and other countries.^[83] Intramammary administration of ketoprofen reduced SCC and damage to the blood-milk barrier, decreasing concentrations of IgG in milk during LPS-induced mastitis.^[84] Ketoprofen alone had positive effects on chronic mastitis,^[85] although effects on acute mastitis were less clear.^[83,86] Carprofen, like meloxicam, is a COX-2 selective, single-dose, long-acting NSAID to treat bovine mastitis.^[73,87] In cows with mastitis, carprofen reduced heart rate, rectal temperature and udder swelling.^[88] In cows with *E. coli* mastitis, carprofen reduced rectal temperature and promoted ruminal motility.^[89] There is a growing recognition of NSAIDs to manage inflammation, pain and endotoxin production in cows with mastitis.^[90] In Denmark, 72% of veterinarians use NSAIDs alone for mastitis, especially if caused by gram-negative bacteria.^[91] Some NSAIDs synergize with antibiotics in treatment of mastitis, such as meloxicam or ketoprofen plus gentamicin.^[90] In addition, some NSAIDs (e.g., meloxicam) can block virulence genes, prevent hemolysis, downregulate expression of genes related to biofilm formation, and inhibit *S. aureus* growth.^[90] We inferred that NSAIDs have potential to fully substitute for antibiotics in treating mastitis in cows in the absence of bacterial growth or for most gramnegative infections. Furthermore, since the primary mechanism of action for NSAIDs against bovine mastitis is non-bacterial, resistant strains should not affect efficacy.

HERBAL MEDICINE

Herbal medicines are derived from natural plants and have a long history of medicinal value, with limited or no side effects compared to antibiotics. The medicinal value of herbs are often due to their metabolites (e.g., phenolic acids, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and volatile oils) that have antibacterial, antioxidant, and antiinflammatory capabilities.^[92] Many herbal

medicines have antibacterial ability. For example, Red ginger had good bactericidal effects on *Staph epidermidis*, *S. aureus*, and *S. agalactiae* derived from bovine mastitis;^[93] the bactericidal mechanism is curcumin and gingerol that kill bacteria by disrupting their extracellular membrane.^[93] Biofilm is a key virulence factor to increase resistance of mastitis-derived methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA); however, Maize whiskers significantly inhibited biofilm production by MRSA strains.^[94] Essential oils are secondary metabolites of plants with antimicrobial properties that do not stimulate drug resistance with prolonged use.^[95] Essential oils (Oregano essential, Thyme essential, Carvacrol essential, and Thymol) killed more than 30 species of *Staphylococci*.^[95] Several other herbal medicines and their extracts, including *Terminalia Chebula*, Purslane and Dandelion also had bactericidal activity against various mastitis pathogens.^[96] Mastitis occurs when the immune system of the mammary gland fails to defend against bacterial invasion; therefore, it is very important to enhance immune activity to prevent and treat mastitis. Dandelion has free radical scavenging, antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory functions^[97] and in a murine mammary gland infection model with *S. aureus*, Dandelion downregulated the inflammatory response.^[98] Vitexin treatment increased T-AOC, SOD, GSH-PX, CAT enzyme activity during *S. aureus* infection, both in vitro and in vivo.^[99] Baicalin, the bioactive component of *Scutellaria baicalensis georgi*, reduced expression of inflammatory factors and apoptosis of bMECs in cows with LPS-induced mastitis. Baicalein protected the mammary gland, reducing mastitis-induced damage.^[100,101] The curative effect of mangostin on LPS-induced mastitis was attributed to suppression of inflammatory cytokine production, particularly the NF- κ B and NLRP3 inflammasome.^[102] Geniposide and ploydatin was anti-inflammatory by interfering with expression of TLR4 and TLR2 and reducing expression of TNF- α , IL1 β , and IL-6.^[103,104] Immunity has a decisive role in occurrence, development and clearance of mastitis. Cows with robust immunity are often able to clear pathogenic bacteria during invasion of the udder. In addition to their powerful antibacterial influence, essential oils can be used as an alternative to antibiotics to improve feed efficiency, nutrient use, and animal health.^[95,105] Dietary supplementation with black seed oil, chamomile oil, or cretian origanum oil starting 8 weeks before calving enhanced immunity in dairy cows.^[105] Furthermore, addition of essential oils to cow diets improved milk production, milk quality, udder health, and immunity.^[105] A Chinese herbal preparation containing 18 herbal medicines, including *Astragalus radix*, *Platycladus stem*, *Crataegus fructus*, and *Chuanxiong*, greatly promoted productivity in late-lactation cows exposed to heat stress.^[106] In summary, herbal medicines contain bioactive components with great value in preventing and treating bovine mastitis,

with mechanisms of action similar to antibiotics, but without the presence of antibiotic residues in milk.^[107] However, some bacteria are naturally resistant to herbal compounds and others develop resistance over time.^[108,109] Moreover, few herbal medicines have been approved by the FDA for clinical use, mainly due to the complexity of their composition and the difficulty to accurately assess efficacy and safety,^[110] although at least some of these issues can be readily addressed.

After surveying the ethno-veterinary practices in India information regarding the plants viz. *Albizia amara*, *Allium sativum*, *Aloe vera*, *Andrographis serpyllifolia*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Citrus aurantifolia*, *Coccinia grandis*, *Curcuma longa*, *Euphorbia tirucalli*, *Fumaria officinalis*, *Leucas aspera*, *Litsea glutinosa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Musa paradisiaca*, *Ocimum tenuiflorum*, *Piper nigrum*, *Psidium guajava*, *Salvadora persica*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Terminalia arjuna*, *Cissus quadrangularis*, etc.

Sr. No.	latin name	Sanskrit name	english name	family	Venacular name	chemical composition probable responsible for anti inflammatory activity
1	aloe vera	kumari /ghrita	kumari /ghrita	asphodelaceae	ghee kunwar	acemannum, campesterol lupenol, salicylic acid
2	curcuma longa linn	haritika	haritika	zingiberaceae	haldi	curcumin, volatile oil
3	calcium oxide	chuna	chuna	—	chuna	cao+h2=ca(oh)2
4	brassica rapa l	sarshapa /siddhartha	sarshapa /siddhartha	brassicaceae	sarson	glucosinolates, hydroxycinnamic acid, flavonoid, anthocyanins
5	citrus limon osbeck	nimbu /jambira	nimbu /jambira	rutaceae	nimbu, zaghi	flavonoid, citric acid, ascorbic acid, minrals, phenols
6	cissus quadrangularis	asthishrinkhala	asthishrinkhala	vitaceae	hadjor	ketosteroids, luteolin, flavonoid terpenoid, calcium salt

STEAM CELL BASED THEARAPY

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) are non-specialized pluripotent cells capable of self-renewal and differentiation into specific cell types, with potential for tissue regeneration. As they are easily accessible, their therapeutic competence is of interest.^[111] MSCs from fetal bovine bone marrow (BM-MSC) and adipose tissue (AT-MSC) reduced growth of *S. aureus* in vitro.^[112] Intramammary administration of AT-MSC in dairy cows killed *S. aureus* in the udder without side effects.^[113] A recent study used MSCs from umbilical cords and their extracellular vesicles to treat subclinical mastitis.^[114] MSCs may have an immunomodulatory role by releasing bioactive components and promoting repair of damaged tissues in dairy cows with mastitis.^[113,114]

NANOTECHNOLOGY BASED THERAPY

Nanotechnology-based drug delivery enables drugs to be deposited, sustained and slowly released at target locations, thereby overcoming some limitations of conventional drugs, including antibiotic resistance.^[115] Self-assembly tilmicosin nanogel was used on cows with *S. aureus* mastitis and had a higher cure rate compared to a conventional treatment group.^[116] Cinnamon oil and silver nanoparticles were bactericidal against *S. agalactiae*.^[117] Polyherbal nanocolloids from Dandelion, Cinnamon, Phyllanthus emblica, Terminalia, and Citronella had efficient, dose-dependent antibacterial ability against mastitis-derived pathogens.^[118]

PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) has much potential for treating bovine mastitis.^[119] A non-toxic photosensitizer is activated to produce ROS that kills bacteria by altering its cell membranes and DNA.^[120] In cows with subclinical mastitis, PDT was bactericidal against *S. uberis* and coagulase negative *S. aureus* (CNS).^[121] Furthermore, in sheep with mastitis, PDT reduced CNS, *Streptococcus* spp. And *E. coli* within udders.^[122] Though PDT has much promise to treat mastitis, the method is still in initial research stages. Improvements in the photosensitizer, light sources and oxygen supply are needed to strengthen the effectiveness of action and reduce adverse side effects.^[123]

ACOUSTIC PULSE THERAPY

Acoustic pulse therapy (APT) is another antibiotic-free strategy to treat bovine mastitis. Cows with mastitis can be treated by APT devices using low-power acoustic pulses to penetrate deep tissue and disperse pressure waves over a broad region of udders.^[124] In addition, APT can activate immune cells and repair damaged tissue.^[124] Similarly, APT was more effective for treating mastitis caused by *E. coli* compared to *Streptococcus*,^[125] with APT-treated cows producing an addition 500 L milk in a 305-day lactation.^[125]

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PROSPECTIVES

Mastitis affects animal welfare and causes economic and production losses by deteriorating milk quality, reducing production performance, increased culling rate, cost of treatment, and due to mortality associated with per acute form of the disease. Several groups of microbial organisms can cause both clinical and subclinical forms of the disease. Subclinical mastitis is economically more important compared to clinical mastitis due to its ability to deteriorate milk quality to such a level that it cannot be detected grossly but will affect the overall quality. Several well established and economic conventional diagnostic techniques are

available for the diagnosis of mastitis but lacks sensitivity and specificity. They cannot be used extensively in the current dairy production sector since they cannot provide rapid results. Recently developed advanced diagnostic tools used for diagnosis of etiological agents in mastitis are easy to use, rapid and sensitive but still lack considerable specificity. Such technique lack economic sustainability due to the requirement of technical assistance, advanced equipment, and infrastructure facilities.

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